

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: *This article discusses the basics of education and upbringing, the importance of the school as a foundation, and the content of the current educational process. In addition, from the first days of his presidency, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev addressed the issues of training modern, scientific, qualified personnel in our country, educating young people as highly spiritual.*

Keywords: *material technology, methodology, education, upbringing, skills, corruption, director, scientific-philosophical and dynamic worldview, management, management.*

Educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and nationalism is an urgent task. This requires strengthening education and upbringing in the family and in schools. Today, measures are being taken in our country to form a harmoniously developed generation, to bring up young people spiritually, morally and physically healthy, to make them active participants in the ongoing reforms, including a modern system of preschool education, 11-year general secondary education. Educational institutions and branches of prestigious foreign universities are being established. In the modern social environment, the scientific-philosophical and dynamic worldview should be mainly scientific and philosophical, and the religious worldview should be developed in the interests of building a secular state in the Republic.

The school plays an important role in helping students develop their talents and abilities. In recent years, a lot of work has been done to develop the material and technical base of schools, to further develop the methods of teachers, and a number of things are still being done. If we look at the history of many developed countries in the world, we see that efforts to change the life of society as a whole began, first of all, with the education system, from kindergarten to school, because without changing schools,

one cannot change society¹. The school is the basis of education and upbringing. From the first days of his presidency, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid special attention to the issues of training modern, scientific and qualified personnel in our country, educating young people as people of high spirituality. At a time when we are trying to make such a state one of the highest states, it is unfortunate that there are people among us who are selfish, who think only of their own interests and who are able to live happily in their time.

At a time when the head of state is struggling to eradicate corruption, we can say that those who are burning the hearth of corruption are traitors to the state. For example, it is surprising that almost 80-90 percent of school staff are close to the principal. You know what it's like to be here. If he is late for class, if he doesn't come to school for other work, even if he doesn't have a teaching method, he is close to the principal. The principal can't speak harshly to him. So when I tell an employee that he or she is close, he or she will say that he or she is not a bad person. He cannot be fired without knowledge. Because we know that, as we said above, he is a close person to the director. When there are such problems, there are various conflicts in the teaching staff. At this point, the leader may be hesitant to make a fair decision.

It is no coincidence that the solution to such problems is the opening of the direction of education management in our scientific institutions and higher education institutions from 2019, which is called "School Management". In order to achieve the strategic goals set by our country, one of the most important issues is the training of potential leaders. Today, raising the leadership potential of young people in management and at the same time teaching them the moral values of our people is a modern requirement of the education system of management. The basic concepts of the organization and management of the educational process and their content, as well as the theoretical aspects of education management and methods of its application in the management of educational institutions are presented. to take into account the need to have not only theoretical knowledge in the field of management, but also to apply it in school practice, to make correct and consistent decisions in the coordination and management of the activities of the staff of the educational institution obtained.

¹ <https://goaravetisyan.ru/uz/sovremennye-trebovaniya-k-kachestvu-obrazovaniya-sovremennye/>

Management system is an image of community life, an integrated social mechanism that has an integrative character as its psychological climate and performs a number of functions in the context of the interaction of the main components of governance (subjects, goals, content and methods of action, attitudes) At the same time, the reforms being implemented by our state pay special attention to the requirements for the leading officials of our country and the essence of their content. Throughout their careers, young people in government must pay special attention to national universal and moral values, and to the protection of human freedoms and rights. This will help them to feel that their happiness has a place in life. 'p work is underway. Today, the opening of part-time and evening departments of higher education, the opening of quotas for admission to higher education institutions, the beginning of distance learning are the main reforms in the field of education. At the same time, there are still a number of problems that hinder the active participation of educational institutions, and to prevent these problems, we need to engage students and at the same time create opportunities for them. In recent years, practical work on the organization of all stages of the education system in our country in accordance with modern requirements has entered a decisive stage.

As our President said; "The more educated our children are in school, the faster the high-tech economy will develop and solve many social problems. If we say that the threshold of a new Uzbekistan begins with school, we think that all our people will support this idea." The main part of the reforms in the field of education is reforms in the higher education system. If we say that the threshold of a new Uzbekistan begins with school, we think that all our people will support this idea. The Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the Presidential Decree dated October 8, 2019 to develop the social sphere and the economy based on advanced educational technologies, serves as a prelude to new reforms in the field. That is why the head of our state pays special attention to attracting leading specialists from South Korea, England, Japan, China, Russia and other countries to the educational process, opening branches of foreign universities in our country, creating opportunities for our youth to study or study abroad. . At the initiative of the President, the granting of academic and organizational, financial independence to higher education institutions and the expansion of councils and powers will fully implement the state policy in the field of education, the provision of quality

educational services and the tasks set by our government. It will create ample opportunities for the training of potential personnel who will determine the development of our country.

In short, it is not only our task to continue the work of the head of our state to raise the level of radical reforms in the field of education and upbringing, to bring up a new generation of personnel capable of taking responsibility for the fate and future of our country. rather it should be our sacred duty

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